

Guards

Guards are a way to augment pattern matching with more complex checks. They are allowed in a predefined set of constructs where pattern matching is allowed.

Not all expressions are allowed in guard clauses, but only a handful of them. This is a deliberate choice. This way, Elixir (and Erlang) can make sure that nothing bad happens while executing guards and no mutations happen anywhere. It also allows the compiler to optimize the code related to guards efficiently.

List of allowed expressions

You can find the built-in list of guards [in the Kernel module](#). Here is an overview:

- comparison operators (`==`, `!=`, `===`, `!==`, `>`, `>=`, `<`, `<=`)
- strictly boolean operators (`and`, `or`, `not`). Note `&&`, `||`, and `!` sibling operators are **not allowed** as they're not *strictly* boolean - meaning they don't require arguments to be booleans
- arithmetic unary and binary operators (`+`, `-`, `*`, `/`, `**`, `/`)
- `in` and `not in` operators (as long as the right-hand side is a list or a range)
- "type-check" functions (`is_list/1`, `is_number/1`, etc.)
- functions that work on built-in datatypes (`abs/1`, `map_size/1`, etc.)

The module `Bitwise` also includes a handful of [Erlang bitwise operations as guards](#).

Macros constructed out of any combination of the above guards are also valid guards - for example, `Integer.is_even/1`. For more information, see the "Defining custom guard expressions" section shown below.

Why guards

Let's see an example of a guard used in a function clause:

```
def empty_map?(map) when map_size(map) == 0, do: true
def empty_map?(map) when is_map(map), do: false
```

Guards start with the `when` keyword, which is followed by a boolean expression (we will define the grammar of guards more formally later on).

Writing the `empty_map?/1` function by only using pattern matching would not be possible (as pattern matching on `%{}` would match every map, not empty maps).

Where guards can be used

In the example above, we show how guards can be used in function clauses. There are several constructs that allow guards; for example:

- function clauses:

```
def foo(term) when is_integer(term), do: term
def foo(term) when is_float(term), do: round(term)
```

- `case` expressions:

```
case x do
  1 -> :one
  2 -> :two
  n when is_integer(n) and n > 2 -> :larger_than_two
end
```

- anonymous functions (`fn`s):

```
larger_than_two? = fn
  n when is_integer(n) and n > 2 -> true
  n when is_integer(n) -> false
end
```

- custom guards can also be defined with `defguard/1` and `defguardp/1`. A custom guard is always defined based on existing guards.

Other constructs are `for`, `with`, `try/rescue/catch/else`, and the `match?/2`.

Failing guards

In guards, when functions would normally raise exceptions, they cause the guard to fail instead. For example, the `length/1` function only works with lists. If we use it with anything else, a runtime error is raised:

```
iex> length("hello")
** (ArgumentError) argument error
```

However, when used in guards, the corresponding clause simply fails to match:

```
iex> case "hello" do
...>   something when length(something) > 0 ->
...>     :length_worked
...>   _anything_else ->
...>     :length_failed
...> end
:length_failed
```

In many cases, we can take advantage of this. In the code above, we used `length/1` to both check that the given thing is a list *and* check some properties of its length (instead of using `is_list(something)` and `length(something) > 0`).

Defining custom guard expressions

As mentioned before, only the expressions listed in this page are allowed in guards. However, we can take advantage of macros to write custom guards that can simplify our programs or make them more domain-specific. At the end of the day, what matters is that the *output* of the macros (which is what will be compiled) boils down to a combinations of the allowed expressions.

Let's look at a quick case study: we want to check that a function argument is an even or odd integer. With pattern matching, this is impossible to do since there are infinite integers, and thus we can't pattern match on the single even/odd numbers. Let's focus on checking for even numbers since checking for odd ones is almost identical.

Such a guard would look like this:

```
def my_function(number) when is_integer(number) and rem(number, 2) == 0 do
  # do stuff
end
```

This would be repetitive to write every time we need this check, so, as mentioned at the beginning of this section, we can abstract this away using a macro. Remember that defining a function that performs this check wouldn't work because we can't use custom functions in guards. Use `defguard` and `defguardp` to create guard macros. Here's an example:

```
defmodule MyInteger do
  defguard is_even(value) when is_integer(value) and rem(value, 2) == 0
end
```

and then:

```
import MyInteger, only: [is_even: 1]

def my_function(number) when is_even(number) do
  # do stuff
end
```

While it's possible to create custom guards with macros, it's recommended to define them using `defguard` and `defguardp` which perform additional compile-time checks.

Multiple guards in the same clause

There exists an additional way to simplify a chain of `or`s in guards: Elixir supports writing "multiple guards" in the same clause. This:

```
def foo(term) when is_integer(term) or is_float(term) or is_nil(term),
  do: :maybe_number
def foo(_other),
  do: :something_else
```

can be alternatively written as:

```
def foo(term)
  when is_integer(term)
  when is_float(term)
  when is_nil(term) do
  :maybe_number
end

def foo(_other) do
  :something_else
end
```

If each guard expression always returns a boolean, the two forms are equivalent. However, recall that if any function call in a guard raises an exception, the entire guard fails. So this function will not detect empty tuples:

```
defmodule Check do
  # If given a tuple, map_size/1 will raise, and tuple_size/1 will not be evaluated
  def empty?(val) when map_size(val) == 0 or tuple_size(val) == 0, do: true
  def empty?(_val), do: false
end

Check.empty?({}) #=> true
Check.empty?({}) #=> false # true was expected!
```

This could be corrected by ensuring that no exception is raised, either via type checks like `is_map(val)` and `map_size(val) == 0`, or by checking equality instead, like `val == %{}`.

It could also be corrected by using multiple guards, so that if an exception causes one guard to fail, the next one is evaluated.

```
defmodule Check do
  # If given a tuple, map_size/1 will raise, and the second guard will be evaluated
  def empty?(val)
    when map_size(val) == 0
    when tuple_size(val) == 0,
    do: true

  def empty?(_val), do: false
end

Check.empty?({}) #=> true
Check.empty?({}) #=> true
```